

Forward – Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions

D8.2 Project website and online platform

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I - A website promoting the Forward project

The Grant Agreement points out the importance of developing a project website with standard project information such as “objectives, funding, partners, work packages, academic publications and results of the project”

Thus, partners developed, from the start of the project, an online page showcasing Forward activities. This website, covering the requested project information aimed at forming a first communication channel for Forward. It was available to the partners at M6 and allowed an early communication of the project.

Items covered by the website:

- Outermost regions
- Forward objectives
- Work plan
- Consortium
- Upcoming events

[Home](#) → [About Forward](#)

Outermost Regions

European union has 9 outermost regions

- Azores (PT)
- Canary Islands (ES)
- Guadeloupe (FR)
- French Guiana (FR)
- Madeira (PT)
- Martinique (FR)
- Mayotte (FR)
- Saint Martin (FR)
- Réunion (FR)

Integral part of the Union, the Outermost Regions have unique potential and assets which can benefit the Union. They provide a European presence in strategic areas of the world, and have exceptional geographical and geological characteristics which make them useful laboratories for research and innovation in scientific domains relevant of the future such as biodiversity, terrestrial and marine ecosystems, pharmacology, renewable energies, and the space sciences.

II - An Online platform, promoting the OR Research and Innovation capacities

A - Online Platform objectives

The Grant Agreement of the project foresees under WP8 the creation of “*a lively online platform for communication, practice sharing, training and multiactor and cross-sectorial cooperation.*”

The grant agreement set the following goals for the online platform:

- keep all partners actively involved in the project through collaborative project management tools allowing actors to share agendas, news, funding opportunities, and final reports,
- store and disseminate knowledge and tools (existing and new ones) among R&I communities of each region, including a visualisation tool exploring data collected in WP2,
- inform stakeholders of the progress and development of the project.

Regarding objective 2, as the consortium has been already using an online collaborative project management solution since M1, the platform was designed in a complementary manner to this existing solution.

Based on the latter and the general FORWARD objectives the partners designed the platform to become a showcase for OR Research and innovation excellence. It pursues the following revised objectives:

- i) increase the visibility and contribute to the recognition of Research and Innovation excellence existing in the Outermost Regions by presenting R&I expertise, projects and stakeholders
- ii) disseminate the Research and Innovation performance and capacities of outermost regions, including a visualisation tool exploring data collected in WP2
- iii) inform stakeholders and international community of the progress and achievements of the Forward project

B - Platform description

The platform is addressed to a wide public comprising European, national and regional authorities; potentials partners from European organisations and general public. It allows a wider visibility of the research and innovation capacities of the Outermost Regions and gives to the OR and European research and innovation communities access to data to be used for dissemination as well as developing new collaborations.

The platform is designed in order to propose to the end-users an easy access, with a smooth and functional browsing, to a large spectre of information:

- Outermost regions general descriptions and regional indicators

- Research and innovation thematic
- Stakeholders from OR Research and innovation communities
- Research and innovation projects in the OR
- News
- Events
- Presentation of the Forward project

The information is easily accessible via 3 entry points: (i) the regions, (ii) Research and innovation thematic and (iii) a map showing an interactive visualisation of OR projects and research communities.

This responsive platform is based on the WordPress Content Management System, allowing easy integration and update of the data. It also collects traffic flows information thanks to the google analytics tool.

C - Development process of the platform

M3 Nexa issues a call for quotation to select an external website developer. Unfortunately the amount foreseen by the project for the build of such platform was not sufficient and candidates indicated not being able to respond.

M4 Project manager agrees with postponing the deadline of this deliverable in order to issue another call for quotations with a larger budget

M5 Nexa issues a second call for quotations

M7 The subcontractor is selected

M8 The task leader creates a Platform correspondents network (See annex 2): each region designates a regional correspondent in charge of integrating and updating the information related to their region (projects, actors, events and news)

M9 The consortium agrees on the proposed design for the platform (See Annex 3)

M11 Each Region via their regional delegates receives access code to the platform and assists to an online training, demonstrating the Platform front and back offices

Each member of the correspondents Network receives a WordPress user guide and starts including Regional content (See Annex 4)

The regions validate a list of 9 thematic to be showcased on the platform (See Annex 5 - each region is in charge of drafting the challenges, assets and fields of investigations/expertise of Outermost Regions for one thematic)

M13 The platform is delivered to the consortium.

M13 The regional correspondents finalise the content of their region. Partners send their feedback to task leader Nexa.

The platform is validated by the consortium

The platform is launched and takes the place of the actual Forward website, using the same URL that was used for the communication of the project at the start of the project: <https://www.forward-h2020.eu/>

The final report of DEL 8.2 is delivered

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D - Platform access

The platform can be accessed by following the link below:

<https://forward-h2020.eu/regions/>

III - Annexes

Annex 1: Forward landing page

<https://www.forward-h2020.eu/>

- Outermost regions
- Forward objectives
- Work plan
- Consortium
- Upcoming events

FORWARD OBJECTIVES

FORWARD is funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 programme

Grant agreement ID: 824550

Boosting Research Excellence & Innovation Capacity in Outermost Regions

Overall objectives :

1. Improve ORs' excellence in research and their innovation potential to
2. Improve their participation in EU research and innovation funded projects
3. Link research activities with territorial development

Specific objectives:

- To map outermost regions' ecosystems in research and innovation to underline strengths, weaknesses and potentials for growth for each OR;
- To identify actual and future fields of excellence and competitive advantages of

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Annex 2: OR platform regional delegates network

Region	Name	Organisation	E-mail address	Training	Received access code and user guide
Azores	Lina SILVEIRA	FRCT	Lina.FM.Silveira@azores.gov.pt	v	v
Canary	Antonella PUGLIESE	ITC	mpugliese@itccanarias.org	v	v
Canary	Javier ROO	ACISI	froofil@gobiernodecanarias.org	Represented by ITC	
Guadeloupe	Sophie LARRIEU	REG GUA	sophie.larrieu@cr-guadeloupe.fr	Absent	v
French Guiana	Karine LEOPOLD	CTG	karine.leopold@ctguyane.fr	v	v
La Réunion	Fanny MAZELLA	Nexa	fanny.mazella@nexa.re	v	v
Madeira	Élia VIEIRA	UMa/ Ardit	elia.vieira@staff.uma.pt	v	v
Martinique	Murielle ALEXANDRINE	CTM	murielle.alexandrine@collectivitedemartinique.mq	Represented by Tania	v
Martinique	Tania REMY	CTM	tania.remy@collectivitedemartinique.mq	v	v
Mayotte	Hadel LAOU-MADI	CG Mayotte	hadel.laou-madi@cg976.fr	v	v
Saint Martin	Junisa GUMBS	COM	junisa.gumbs@com-saint-martin.fr	v	v

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Annex 3: OR Platform Design

<http://studio.koredge.fr/forward/>

The screenshot displays the 'Forward' platform interface. On the left is a vertical navigation menu under the heading 'REFONTE GRAPHIQUE'. The menu items are: 'Home et Region', 'HOME', 'HOME ZOOM CARTE', 'REGION - PROFILE', 'REGION - DASHBOARD NIV 1', 'REGION - DASHBOARD NIV 2', 'REGION - STAKEHOLDERS', 'REGION - FICHE STAKEHOLDER', 'REGION - PROJECTS', 'REGION - FICHE PROJECT', 'REGION - NEWS', 'REGION - RESOURCES', 'Navigation principale', and 'REGIONS'. The main content area features a large banner image of a mountain range with the text 'Discover research and innovation initiatives in Outermost regions'. Below the banner is a search bar with the placeholder 'Grab your search or let you guide' and a magnifying glass icon. Underneath the search bar are suggestions: 'Try this: Blue economy, Energy transition, Space science, More suggestions'. Below the banner is a section titled 'Research & innovation of EU's outermost regions'. This section contains two blue cards: 'Regions' and 'Thematics'. The 'Regions' card has a sub-heading, a paragraph of placeholder text, a 'Select a region' dropdown menu, and a 'See our regions' button. The 'Thematics' card has a sub-heading, a paragraph of placeholder text, a 'Select a thematic' dropdown menu, and a 'See our thematics' button. The top of the page includes the 'Forward' logo, a search bar, and navigation links for 'Regions', 'Thematics', 'R&I communities', 'Projects', 'Resources', 'News', and 'About Forward'. There are also social media icons and a 'Contact' button.

Annex 4: WordPress Guidelines

Available on the Forward Drive

https://drive.google.com/file/d/18D1lRulgLbB6pDJUmP5TM0f67rz0wqq5/view?usp=s_haring

1.2 Common expressions

There are a number of terms that will be used throughout this presentation.

Frontend: this is the site that can be seen by everyone.

Backend: this is the WordPress workspace where the site is edited.

Frontend-editing: WordPress edition directly from the site in "see" mode.

Blocks: these are the construction elements that make up the different pages of the site.

Plugin: these are modules such as news, banners and slideshows for example. Generally, plugins are the specific elements of your site, except for text + image blocks. These are largely related to the "list" mode of WordPress, which we will see later.

Tree structure: this is the structure of the pages on which the site is built. It is represented in WordPress and on your site in the same way.

Uploader: send an online file to your site, in the media library.

 koredge

- NEXA : <https://www.forward-h2020.eu/> -

Notes

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Annex 5: OR Platform, 9 Research and innovation thematic validated by the regions

Validation of 9 R&I Thematics	Region in charge of drafting the description
Agriculture, applied life sciences, biotechnology, and biosystems engineering	Guyane
Biodiversity conservation and restoration	La Réunion
Earth system & Universe Sciences	Azores
Energy transition	Canary
Health, applied Medical Technologies, Diagnostics and Therapies	Guadeloupe
Information and Communications Technology	Madeira
Marine sciences & technologies	Mayotte
Social sciences and social innovation	Martinique
Tourism, eco-tourism, nature tourism, cultural tourism	Saint Martin

Annex 6: Online OR Platform

<https://forward-h2020.eu/regions/>

**Research & innovation of EU's
outermost regions**